

EXPERIENCE OF DISTANCE TRAINING OF DOCTORS IN THE BASICS OF INTENSIVE CARE FOR PATIENTS WITH COVID-19

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Abstract

Today, the emphasis of medical education is shifting to the demand for the skills of oxygen therapy, the implementation of auxiliary and artificial ventilation. The article presents the results of an analysis of distance learning for doctors of various specialties on the basics of intensive care for patients with COVID-19. The problems faced by teachers and students are considered.

Keywords: distance learning, COVID-19 intensive care.

COVID-19 pandemic has directly affected not only the healthcare system, but also the content of medical education itself. Most of the formed clinical competencies of a doctor are inextricably linked with personal presence in the learning process, because our communication skills with patients and practical manipulations are difficult to master remotely [1]. Today, the focus of medical education is shifting to the demand for new skills, such as emergency care, oxygen therapy, assisted ventilation and mechanical ventilation. New methods of diagnosing and treating patients in conditions of increased infectious danger, which require well-coordinated teamwork and knowledge of new algorithms of actions, have become relevant [2].

Like doctors around the world, doctors of our country are faced with the problem of poor knowledge of a new infection and the lack of protocols to combat the coronavirus pandemic, as well as a lack of qualified personnel for respiratory therapy. In this connection, the need for training in practical skills of tracheal intubation, oxygen therapy and artificial lung ventilation (ALV) has sharply increased. But due to the current epidemiological situation, the training had to take place remotely.

Most teachers took up self-education and urgently studied recommendations and instructions for working with various services and platforms, learned how to record video lectures and webinars, and learn the basics of distance learning. D. Taylor defines distance learning: "This is individual learning from specially prepared educational materials, printed or electronic, supported by integrated educational resources and processes such as face-to-face learning, practical experience, feedback and support for students." "Distance learning is a blended learning using various coordinated modalities and methods that contribute to the implementation of the curriculum and effective learning" [4]. A full-fledged training of teachers in such a short time was not possible and was reduced to instructive internal meetings, short webinars from the expert community.

Distance learning was initially organized only in telegram channels and on the basis of video lectures posted on the website of the Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers. Video lectures were conducted using the Internet platforms ZOOM, Microsoft Teams, Webex, and more. At the first stage, lectures were conducted by the teaching staff for the regions, as well as broadcasts of scientific and practical video conferences from various countries (Russia, USA, Turkey, South Korea, Great Britain, Ukraine) for doctors via videoconferencing.

Power Point presentations were used as visual materials, own photo and video materials of the department, illustrative material from open sources, materials of online conferences. Basic medical manipulations with a detailed analysis of the algorithm of actions on mannequins were demonstrated during the webinar, receiving or providing timely feedback. At the end of the training, a test was conducted on the material covered, after which the doctor could receive a certificate of completion of the training by e-mail.

In the process of completing tasks, students received timely advice and feedback from their teachers. Teachers noted the active participation of students in the learning process (90%), increased responsibility (95%), empathy for the current situation (95%) and readiness to respond to any changes in the learning process (92%).

For the period from March 2020 to September 2020, we have trained over 800 resuscitators at the Department of Anesthesiology and Resuscitation of the Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers. In September - October 2020, doctors of various specialties were trained in the traditional format at different bases, by different teachers, according to a unified program for 18 credits. These programs made it possible to obtain the missing knowledge and form the necessary skills for those health workers who were additionally admitted to the ICU staff during the coronavirus pandemic.

To achieve an educational result, it was necessary to create a team of participants, develop content and a program. Before the introduction of new projects, it was necessary to conduct quality control, to identify errors.

As part of the USAID project “Strengthening the resilience of health systems in response to COVID-19”, questionnaires were developed to study the need for doctors in educational programs and types of additional training.

The questionnaire developed for this study consisted of 23 questions in several blocks: questions concerning; issues related to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic; questions about the level of personal computer proficiency and Internet skills.

The vast majority of respondents are satisfied with the training and speak positively about the organization of the learning process. The majority of respondents (67%) highly appreciated both the way teachers present educational information and its content, 28% noted that they would like to receive more additional material on the topics studied, for 4% the taught material did not reveal anything new, for 1% of students the material remained incomprehensible.

Over 90% of physicians asked to include more questions on the basics of oxygen therapy, physiology

and pathophysiology of acute respiratory failure, as well as noninvasive lung ventilation and artificial lung ventilation regimens in the curriculum. In the context of the pandemic, in conditions of limited resources and short courses, these issues were covered very briefly. The issues of oxygen therapy were not raised in the bachelor's program of study.

We conducted a SWOT analysis of the questionnaire on training opportunities in intensive care for COVID-19, the results of which are shown in Table 1.

Most often, doctors encountered technical problems associated with a sharp increase in the number of users on the site at the same time, unstable mobile communications, and low Internet speed. In addition, resuscitators did not always have the opportunity to attend lectures, because they were trained on the job and provided care to patients.

In this connection, it was necessary to solve the problem by creating full-fledged distance courses and mobile applications. The organization of the educational process based on situational tasks from clinical practice and the introduction of gamification of the educational process to develop practical skills could improve the quality of learning.

Table 1.

SWOT Analysis of the COVID-19 Critical Care Training Opportunities Questionnaire

Strengths	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality equipment; • Prepared team; • Consumables are fully equipped; • Available video materials ; • Resources • Availability of the teacher at any time; • Reproducibility of activities with video recording 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training available; • The different composition of the brigade is taken into account; • Mobile application for learning anywhere; • Distance learning; • Economic efficiency • Team training
Weaknesses	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unstable communication and Internet in the region; • Local attachment to a laptop or computer • Low computer literacy; • Lack of direct contact between the teacher and the student; • Lack of interest from hospital management and doctors themselves; • Basic knowledge of doctors on mechanical ventilation is different 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of motivation among doctors for training; • There is no desire to pass on acquired skills and train nurses; • Without control, they may not engage; • Not all doctors want to be trained; • Potential for unstable feedback from trained clinicians; • Poor knowledge of time management • Difficulties with adapting to the online format

In this situation, the constraints stimulated the search for creative solutions. As part of the USAID project “Strengthening Health Systems Resilience in Response to COVID-19”, we developed an online course “Management of patients with COVID-19 SARI”, consisting of 16 modules, each module consists of several video lessons. [3]. After completing the study of each module, the student must be tested. The course was developed on the basis of WHO materials " Block-modular training on clinical and epidemiological aspects of COVID -19", as well as the online course "Epidemiological Surveillance". The course is a mobile application that is installed on a smartphone or personal computer. The course content can be downloaded and studied without constant access to the Internet.

According to the pilot version of this course, 300 doctors of various specialties and nurses from intensive care units from various regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan were trained. The ultimate goal of this course is the application of already acquired knowledge and skills in a situation different from the one in which the training took place. Clinicians will be able to apply infection prevention and control measures, triage patients in the hospital based on the developed new algorithm; Describe in detail the activities carried out in the intensive care unit and the complications of COVID-19, as well as measures to prevent complications based on the developed algorithm; Follow pandemic ethics issues not previously addressed; Describe the best practices worldwide for ICU management standards.

At the end of the course, we invited doctors to fill out a questionnaire to assess the quality of the distance course. All respondents noted the high informativeness and quality of the educational material. Of the advantages of the course, the following are indicated: constant support of trainers and technical support (100%), cost-effective (99%), convenient learning regardless of the place and time of the student's classes (100%), clarity of the material, especially with video animation (100%), ease of finding information (97%).

Trainers noted the active participation of doctors and nurses in the educational process (90%), and their willingness to respond to any changes in the learning process (92%).

This distance course allowed doctors to gain the missing knowledge and develop the necessary skills during the coronavirus pandemic.

Thus, we recommend the integration of this course into undergraduate and graduate programs in all Medical Universities of Uzbekistan, into clinical residency programs and advanced training programs for anesthesiologists, resuscitators, infectious disease specialists and emergency doctors, as well as advanced training programs for nurses. The combination of various forms of learning: visual methods, problem-based learning,

role-playing games, elements of gamification will allow students to better learn skills and remember them for a long time. "Technological advances are worth nothing if educators are unable to use them. Miracles are not created by computers, but by teachers!" said Craig Barret .

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